

CHARACTERISTICS OF EDUCATIONAL MOTIVATION OF VOCATIONAL VOCATIONAL SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract: This article describes the characteristics of educational motivation in vocational school students and the importance of student motivation in the educational process.

Key words: Vocational school, motivation, Yerkes-Dodson, Professional value, Utilitarian-cognitive.

In order to increase the personal motivation and interest of vocational school students, conducting the lesson individually, reducing the distance between the student and the teacher, i.e. working together, encouraging students during the lesson, It should be explained in relation to everyday life. Motivation is the leading factor that regulates a person's activity and behavior. Any pedagogical interaction with the student will be effective only taking into account the specific characteristics of his motivation. There may be completely different reasons behind the objectively identical actions of vocational students. The sources of motivation for the same action can be completely different. The success or effectiveness of educational activities depends on socio-psychological and socio-pedagogical factors. The strength and structure of motivation also affect the success of educational activities. Yerkes-Dodson¹ according to the law, the effectiveness of educational activities directly depends on the power of motivation.

According to psychological data, any activity arises under the influence of certain motives and takes place only when sufficient conditions are created. Therefore, in order to ensure mastery, acquisition and implementation of learning in the educational process, it is necessary for students to have educational motivation.

Motivation² - these are the processes that determine the movement towards the goal, the factors that influence the activity or passivity of this behavior. The main link of motivation is motivation - a behavioral manifestation of satisfying one's own needs.

American psychologist A. Maslov's positive holistic-dynamic theory of motivation defines five basic needs:

Physiological needs - they are related to the satisfaction of food, water, sexual needs.

The need for security - the need for safety, stability, protection, structure and order;

The need for belonging and love - it involves the desire to associate with a social group

The need for recognition - it includes a desire that is more closely related to the concept of achievement - respect for others and self-esteem

¹ <https://www.healthline.com/health/yerkes-dodson-law#:~:text=The%20Yerkes%2DDodson%20law%20is,inverted%2DU%20model%20of%20arousal.>

² <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Motivation>

The need for self-actualization is the individual's desire for self-realization, actualization of his potential. Then, behind the proposed five-level needs model, Maslow has two more needs: the need for knowledge and understanding and aesthetic needs. The need for knowledge and understanding are cognitive human needs. It is related to the need for truth, the attraction of the unknown, the incomprehensible. This need is closely related to learning motivation. Aesthetic needs are characterized by more fragmentation and uncertainty. They are closely related to conative and cognitive needs.

Motivation is the general name of the process of encouraging vocational school students to engage in effective learning activities and actively develop educational content. In terms of the teacher, it is about the motivation to learn. From the learner's point of view, we are talking about learning motivation. Motivation is a stimulus that causes the activity of a person and determines its direction, especially necessary in the educational process. Taking into account the motivation of educational activities, it should be noted that the concept of motive is closely related to the concept of purpose and need. In a person's personality, they interact and are called the motivational sphere. The term motivational field includes all types of motives: needs, interests, goals, incentives, motives, inclinations, attitudes.

Learning motivation is the general name of the processes, methods, and means of encouraging students to engage in effective learning activities, to actively master the educational content. Figuratively speaking, images of motivation are held together in the hands of teachers (educational motivation, attitude to their professional duties) and students (motivation for learning, internal, self-motivation).

Educational motivation in a vocational school is a specific type of motivation included in a specific activity, in this case, educational activity, educational activity. Like any other type, learning motivation is determined by a number of specific factors.

- ❖ *the educational system itself is determined by the educational institution;*
- ❖ *organizational learning process;*
- ❖ *subjective characteristics of the student;*
- ❖ *the subjective characteristics of the teacher and, first of all, the system of his attitude to the student and the situation;*
- ❖ *distinctive features.*³

The educational activity of vocational school students is motivated by a hierarchy of motives, which is related to either the content of this activity and internal motives related to its implementation, or the need for the student to occupy a certain position in the system of social relations. broad social motives; can be dominant. At the same time, depending on age, there is a correlation of interacting needs and motives, a change in leading dominant needs and their specific hierarchy. Educational motivation consists of several motives that constantly change and enter into new relationships with each other (needs and content of education for students, its motives, goals, feelings, interests).

The formation of motivation is not a simple increase of a positive or negative attitude towards the student, but a complication of the structure of the motivational field, the motives included in it, the emergence of new, more mature, sometimes conflicting attitudes. between them.

³ Kharatova, S. K., & Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2022). Use of innovative technologies in the educational process. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 713-718.

taking into account not only the dominant impulse (motive), but also the entire structure of the motivational sphere of the person. social expectations, claims, emotions, volitional qualities and other socio-psychological characteristics of a person whose characteristics such as orientation, value orientations, attitudes are "pulled". "The concept of motivation in a person ... includes all types of motives: motives, needs, interests, aspirations, goals, drivers, motivational attitudes or dispositions, ideals, etc.

Motivation is the main tool that allows to increase the level of interest of students in the educational process, increases their personal scientific and creative potential. A student who does not have sufficient motivation does not contribute to the development of his knowledge, nor to the science itself. The educational process is classified as a complex activity, therefore there are many motivations for learning, and they can not only be manifested separately in each individual, but also combine to form complex motivational systems.

Student motivation was ignored for a long time. Indeed, in the 21st century, it is one of the most effective ways to improve the learning process and the results of seminars, lectures and sessions held over the years. Motives and motivation are the driving force behind the learning process and assimilation of information and material. It is motivation that is the main tool that allows to increase the level of interest of students in the educational process and increases their personal scientific and creative potential.

They talk about learning motives, motives can be classified according to their direction and content:

Social — (understanding the importance of duty, responsibility, education for the whole society);

Cognitive - (the desire to know more, to be knowledgeable);

Professional value (expanding prospects and interesting work);

Aesthetics (learning is a pleasure, a person's hidden skills and abilities are revealed);

Communicative (the ability to increase your intellectual level and expand your social circle by making new acquaintances),

Status-position (the desire is confirmed in society through education or social activity);

Traditional-historical (established stereotypes that arose in society and were strengthened over time);

Utilitarian-cognitive (desire to study a topic of special interest and learn self-education);

Unconscious motives (based on a complete misunderstanding of the meaning of the received information and a complete lack of interest in the cognitive process).⁴

These motives can combine to form a general motivation for learning. The main idea about the predominance and action of certain motives of education is determined by the student's attitude to education.

One of the most common barriers to learning is the loss of student motivation to continue learning. Loss of motivation can be a serious complication because it is very difficult for the student to concentrate on tasks. It becomes much more difficult to prepare for the implementation of test items, passing exams and completing projects. It is motivation that encourages a person to overcome various difficulties, boredom or fatigue in the process of studying. Without motivation, the learning task loses its meaning. However, those who fear a

⁴ Leontiev A.N. Faoliyat, ong, shaxsiyat. - Moskva.: Poliizdat, 1975. - S. 112-115.

loss of motivation can be easily convinced. The desire and ability to learn can be stimulated by artificial means.

Among the methods of vocational schools to increase motivation, I propose to include the following:

- ❖ *Introducing a system of publishing awards for student success and their outstanding achievements and aspirations;*
- ❖ *To expand the possibilities of self-awareness of students;*
- ❖ *The possibility of introducing an individual system of teaching students also requires objectively changing the place and role of the teacher in the educational process or educational process.⁵*

The educational process should be based on the psychological-pedagogical design of the development of each student, subject-subject relations of the training participants. Maximum focus on the formation of a self-sufficient person is necessary for the competence-based educational process. For this, authoritarian pedagogy, the subject-object type of relationship between student and teacher must be left in the past. In order to increase the student's motivation to study, it is important to know that the new curriculum is built on the principles of developmental education and is based on some completely new educational principles.

When studying the formation of educational motivation in the institution of vocational schools, we took into account the following general rules:

1. Psychological research of motivation and its formation are two sides of the same process of educating the motivational sphere of the student's holistic personality. The study of motivation is to determine its actual level and possible prospects, the zone of proximal development for each student and the group (stream) as a whole. At the same time, in the process of formation of motivation, its new reserves are opened, therefore, real learning and diagnosis are carried out in the process of formation.
2. When organizing the study and formation of motivation, it is necessary to avoid a simplified understanding of them. Reading should not be considered only as a teacher's registration of things that lie on the surface and catch the eye ("wants the student to study and become a highly qualified specialist" or "does not want"), but it should be built as a teacher's penetration of the teacher into the deep laws of the formation of the student as a person and subject of activity.
3. The teacher himself (for example, without waiting for the arrival of a psychologist) can learn and form the student's motivation through long-term observation of students in real life conditions, analysis of repeated comments and actions of students, as a result of which the teacher can sufficiently draw reliable conclusions, determine and correct the ways of its formation.

In conclusion, the above points mean that the importance of motivational pedagogical technologies and psychological effects in improving the educational efficiency of vocational school students is appropriate.

⁵ Мокчанцев Р., Мокчанцева А. Социальная психология. Издательства: Сибирское соглашение, Инфра. — М.: 2001.

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